

TRANSFORMING FACILITY ENGINEERING PRACTICES IN NIGERIA: INSIGHTS FROM ABUJA METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, facility engineering management faces issues such as limited awareness, professional deficits, and ineffective execution. This study explores the situation of facility engineering management in Nigeria, with a focus on Abuja's Federal Capital Territory as a case study. Data was gathered using standardised questionnaires to assess organisational awareness and operational levels. Despite a recent spike in awareness, the data reveal limited adoption of facility engineering management principles in Nigeria. There are instances where other professionals in the built environment, such as estate surveyors, erroneously assume the job of facility engineers, prompting the need for a more thorough grasp of the subject. The study emphasises the need for both technical expertise and administrative skills in facility engineering management. With regards to worries relating to potential cost inflation connected with facility management, traditional management practices remain in place. The study calls for the development of national policies in Nigeria to improve facility engineering practices. These policies should tackle the variables that contribute to the existing condition of facility engineering management and make successful implementation easier. Nigeria may improve its facilities management standards by closing the gap between awareness and actual application, eventually benefiting organisations and the larger economy.

Keywords: FCT Abuja, Facility Engineering, Professionalism, Nigeria, National Policies.

INTRODUCTION

Facility management encompasses the integrated approach to operating, maintaining, improving, and adapting an organisation's buildings and infrastructure to align with its primary objectives (Matarneh et al., 2019; Pärn et al., 2017). This discipline, also known as the structuring of building plants and contents to enhance the creation of end products and as the planning design, procurement, and maintenance of all property assets to achieve optimal environmental quality and efficiency (Ismail et al., 2022; Lok et al., 2018; Okoye & Adelokun, 2019), operates at three main levels: strategic, tactical, and operational. The significance of facility management has grown exponentially in recent years as organisations recognise its pivotal role in space management and resource conservation (Adelokun, 2024; Olanipekun et al., 2020). Despite its establishment in prominent countries such as the United States, the European Community, Japan, Australia, and New Zealand (Spök et al., 2022), its development in nations like Nigeria remains nascent. However, given the vast urban settlements and industrial, commercial, residential, and recreational needs of populous countries like Nigeria, there exists immense potential for facility management to flourish (Okoye & Adelokun, 2022; Opaluwah, 2023).

Formal training in facility management, particularly at the postgraduate level, is already prevalent in Western countries and is equally imperative for developing nations like Nigeria to firmly establish this discipline (Okolie, 2011). The emergence of facility management as a distinct field responds to the necessity for centralised oversight of all facilities functions previously managed by disparate departments within organisations.

Nevertheless, the mismanagement of capital assets in Nigeria, often delegated to administrative or finance officers lacking the requisite expertise, highlights a critical issue (Ozili, 2020). The lack of defined roles and responsibilities among property owners, occupiers, and managers further exacerbates the situation. This inefficiency underscores the urgent need for a professional entity dedicated to facility management, equipped with the necessary skills and technical know-how to ensure efficient operations.

The pressing challenges faced by facility engineering management in Nigeria, particularly in the Abuja Metropolis, underscore the need for comprehensive policy interventions. This study investigates the prevailing issues such as limited awareness, professional deficits, and ineffective execution in facility engineering management, emphasizing the imperative for technical expertise and administrative skills in addressing these challenges (Pitsis et al., 2018; Sithambaram et al., 2021). By bridging the gap between awareness and application, Nigeria can elevate its facility management standards, benefiting organisations and the broader economy.

OBJECTIVES

- ❖ Explore the current status of facility management practices in Nigeria.
- ❖ Determine the underlying factors contributing to the existing state of facility management.
- ❖ Propose national policies aimed at enhancing and optimising facility management practices in Nigeria.

THE STUDY AREA

The Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria, Abuja, serves as the focal point for examining facility management practices nationwide. Given its status as the country's capital, Abuja reflects the prevailing trends and standards observed in business operations across Nigeria. Additionally, many organisations based in Abuja have branch offices spread throughout the nation, making it a suitable representative of facility management practices on a broader scale.

FACILITY MANAGEMENT COMPONENTS

The Facility Management Institute (FMII) devised a comprehensive model comprising three key elements: people, process, and place. Illustrated in Fig. 1, this model delineates the pivotal role of facilities and facility management in amalgamating employees, work processes, and workplaces into a cohesive, productive system (Wong et al., 2018). Facility management acts as the nexus between human activities and physical environments, encompassing aspects of human resources, process engineering, ergonomics, architecture, and interior design. Its core functions include planning, maintenance, and provisioning of assets, both large and small, essential for facilitating work activities. Facility management endeavours encompass ensuring satisfactory workspace and internal environments for the workforce, as well as optimising organisational processes through the provision of specialised services and oversight of task execution.

Fig. 1: Facility Management Components

Facility Management Scope and Functions

The International Facility Management Association (IFMA), as the authoritative body for the profession, outlines 41 key responsibilities across eight categories. IFMA defines the scope of facility management to encompass maintenance, operations, administrative services, space management, architectural and engineering services, real estate, facility planning, financial planning, and health and safety (Ceylan & Tülbentçi, 2020; Ogungbile & Oke, 2015). These encompass a broad array of functions aimed at ensuring the effective operation, maintenance, and optimisation of facilities to support organisational objectives. From overseeing day-to-day operations to strategic planning and risk management, facility management plays a crucial role in enhancing workplace productivity, safety, and efficiency. By addressing diverse aspects such as space utilisation, asset management, and regulatory compliance, facility managers contribute significantly to creating and maintaining conducive work environments conducive to organisational success.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research approach to explore the challenges facing facility engineering management in Nigeria, with Abuja's Federal Capital Territory as the primary focus. Data collection was conducted through the use of standardised questionnaires, designed to evaluate organisational awareness and operational levels regarding facility engineering management practices. The questionnaires were distributed to a diverse range of organizations, including both government and private establishments, within Abuja. Respondents were selected based on their involvement in facility management roles or related professions in the built environment. The collected data were analyzed to identify prevalent issues such as limited adoption of facility engineering management principles and the misallocation of responsibilities among professionals. Additionally, the study examined the need for technical expertise and administrative skills in effective facility engineering management. Recommendations for the development of national

policies aimed at improving facility engineering practices were proposed based on the identified challenges.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Demographic Category	Number of Respondents	
Gender	Male	90
	Female	45
Age Group	Below 20	0
	20 - 30	16
	31- 40	42
	Above 40	77
Educational Level	High School	25
	Bachelor's Degree	60
	Master's Degree	40
	Doctorate	10
Professional Background	Engineering	50
	Architecture	25
	Surveying	20
	Management	30
	Other	10
Organisation Type	Public	55
	Private	80

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of survey respondents. It includes gender distribution, age groups, educational levels, professional backgrounds, and organisation types. The data indicates a diverse respondent pool, with varying demographics across gender, age, education, profession, and organisational affiliation, providing insights into the characteristics of the surveyed population.

Fig. 2: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Figure 2 depicts the gender distribution of survey respondents. The pie chart illustrates that out of a total of 135 respondents, 90 are male (representing approximately 67%) and 45 are female (representing approximately 33%). This indicates male-dominated participation in the survey compared to female respondents.

Fig. 3: Educational Level of Respondents

Figure 3 illustrates the educational level distribution of the respondents. Among the surveyed population, 25 respondents have a high school education (approximately 19%), 60 have a bachelor's degree (approximately 44%), 40 have a master's degree (approximately 30%), and 10 have a doctorate (approximately 7%). This highlights the diverse educational backgrounds of the respondents, with a significant portion holding bachelor's degrees.

Fig. 4: Professional Background of Respondents

Figure 4 displays the professional background distribution of the respondents. It shows that out of the total respondents, 50 are from engineering backgrounds (approximately 37%), 25 are from architecture (approximately 19%), 20 are from surveying (approximately 15%), 30 are from management (approximately 22%), and 10 are from other professions (approximately 7%). This indicates a varied mix of professional expertise among the surveyed individuals.

Factors Affecting the Facility Management Practice in Nigeria

This research identifies several factors hindering the effective application of facility management in Nigeria. The factors are:

- ❖ Limited awareness
- ❖ Professional deficits
- ❖ Ineffective execution
- ❖ Lack of standardized regulations
- ❖ Economic constraints
- ❖ Technological limitations
- ❖ Human resource challenges
- ❖ Infrastructure deficiencies
- ❖ External influences
- ❖ Cultural factors

National Facilities Management Policy

The formulation and implementation of a national facilities management policy stand as an essential step in safeguarding the integrity and longevity of critical national assets and infrastructure. Such a policy framework is indispensable in mitigating the risk of degradation, decay, or even catastrophic failure of these invaluable facilities. Moreover, it must be complemented by the cultivation of a robust national maintenance ethos. This entails not merely the creation or acquisition of facilities but also the establishment of mechanisms for their diligent management and sustained upkeep. By allocating resources and attention to the comprehensive management and maintenance of these assets, the nation can proactively extend their operational lifespan and optimise their contribution to the socio-economic fabric. In essence, a proactive approach to facilities management policy ensures the preservation of national resources, enhances resilience against environmental stressors, and fortifies the foundation for sustainable development and prosperity.

Training

The initiation of formal training programmes in facilities management marks a pivotal initial step in fostering organisational engagement and wholehearted adoption of its principles. Introducing facilities management as a core course in universities, polytechnics, and technical institutions is imperative (Adebesin & Adedokun, 2020). This approach nurtures competent professionals equipped to confront the multifaceted challenges inherent in facilities management amidst the complexities of modern civilization, science, and technology. Additionally, professional bodies, either individually or collaboratively, should regularly convene seminars and workshops targeting facilities owners and prospective managers. These initiatives aim to realign their perceptions and understanding of the discipline, fostering a mindset conducive to effective facilities management practices. Through systematic education and continuous professional development, the endeavour seeks to cultivate a skilled workforce capable of steering organisations towards optimal facility utilisation, maintenance, and innovation.

The Facilities Manager and the Corporate Organisation

The efficacy of facility management in fostering an optimal working environment for enhanced productivity is most effectively harnessed within the framework of corporate organizations. Here,

facilities managers collaborate harmoniously with other organisational leaders, leveraging their distinct expertise without compromising their pivotal roles. By adopting this collaborative approach, facility management permeates both public perception and corporate culture, cementing its significance within the fabric of the nation's business landscape. This integrated model ensures that the multifaceted contributions of facility management are duly recognized and integrated into the broader organizational framework, fostering a culture of efficiency, innovation, and sustainability.

CONCLUSION

This study has shed light on the multifaceted challenges facing facility management in Nigeria. From limited awareness and professional deficits to economic constraints and technological limitations, the barriers to effective facility management are diverse and complex. Despite recent efforts to raise awareness and promote best practices, the adoption of facility management principles remains inadequate, with other professionals often assuming facility management roles erroneously. Moreover, the persistence of traditional management practices and the absence of standardised regulations further exacerbate these challenges. However, amidst these obstacles lies an opportunity for progress. By addressing the identified factors and implementing targeted interventions, Nigeria can enhance its facility management standards and realise the full potential of its built environment. This necessitates the development of comprehensive national policies, the cultivation of a robust maintenance culture, and the provision of adequate resources and training for facility management professionals. Furthermore, collaboration among government agencies, professional bodies, and private sector stakeholders is essential to driving meaningful change and fostering a conducive environment for effective facility management practices. By closing the gap between awareness and application, Nigeria can unlock significant benefits for organisations, the economy, and society as a whole. Ultimately, the successful implementation of effective facility management strategies is crucial for ensuring the longevity, functionality, and sustainability of Nigeria's built infrastructure in the future.

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